

Cerpegin alkaloid and its analogues: Chemical synthesis and pharmacological profiles

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Manuscript received 03 July 2018, revised 06 July 2018, accepted 11 July 2018

This review aims to highlight cerpegin alkaloid, a key compound of the genus *Ceropegia*. It shows significant biological activities and a number of synthetic strategies for synthesis of cerpegin alkaloid have been reported. In recent years its derivatives have raised interest as promising bioactive candidates to explore and improve its pharmacological profile. It is anticipated that this area of chemistry will continue to attract significant research activity in future.

Keywords: Cerpegin alkaloid, *Ceropegia* plant, metalation, proteasome inhibitor, analgesic, antiurolithiatic, antidiabetic.

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1. Introduction

Ceropegia is a genus of plants and belongs to the family

Apocynaceae. The genus *Ceropegia* belongs to the subfamily *Asclepiadaceae* (now called as *Asclepiadoideae*) (milkweeds family)¹⁻⁴. More than 200 species of this genus are known and distributed throughout Africa, southern Asia and Australia⁵. The maximum diversity of *Ceropegia* occurs in South Africa followed by Kenya, Madagascar and India⁶. *Ceropegia*, in general, grow in any type of soils, but a little fertilizer is helpful. Enough light and regular watering are required for proper growth. In wetter soil mix the plant must be allowed to dry between watering. Some special characters of this genus are attractive flytrap flowers, flower design, corolla size, shape and coloring pattern etc. The tuberous root and fleshy stem of *Ceropegia* species are a warehouse of starch, sugars, gum, albuminoid, fats, crude fibre and other valuable phytoconstituents which are routinely used in traditional Indian ayurvedic drugs for the treatment of gastric disorders, diarrhea, dysentery, urinary tract disorders, hepatic disorders and etc.⁷⁻⁹. *Ceropegia intermedia*, *Ceropegia jainii* (Western Ghats, India), *Ceropegia juncea* (Coast of Coromandel, India), *Ceropegia bulbosa* (Western Ghats, India), *Ceropegia noorjahana* (Western Ghats, India) are some selected species found in India¹⁰⁻¹⁵. *Ceropegia juncea*, *Ceropegia bulbosa*, *Ceropegia spiralis* and *Ceropegia noorjahana* are endangered and endemic to India^{1,15,16}. Because of habitat destruction, over exploitation for their edible tuberous roots, poor seed germination, scarcity of pollinators and frequent fungal infection, *Ceropegia juncea*, *Ceropegia bulbosa* etc. are going to rare and endangered category in various places of India. To address limitations of

natural propagation researchers developed micropropagation protocols for *Ceropegia* species to conserve rare and endangered *Ceropegia* plants¹⁷⁻²⁴. The pharmacological importance of the genus *Ceropegia* is mainly due to the presence of a pyridine alkaloid called 'Cerpegin'²⁵. Beside cerpegin alkaloid, several phytochemicals like triterpenes e.g. lup-18-en-3 β -ol, glycosides, flavonoids, polyphenols, steroids, volatile oils etc. are also found in the *Ceropegia* plant extracts. The earlier review gave an account of *in vitro* propagation of genus *Ceropegia* and retrosynthesis of cerpegin²². The objective of the present review is to stimulate the study of chemistry of cerpegin and derivatives in terms of its new chemical synthesis as well as its pharmacological profiles. This review highlights progress in the chemistry of cerpegin since 1991. Special attention is focused upon the expanding reports on methods of its synthesis or synthetic approaches. Virtually all of the efforts on chemistry of cerpegin to date have been covered in this review.

2. Isolation and structure

Ceropegia juncea is reported to be an important source of Ayurvedic drug²⁶. The alcoholic extract of the plant was found to display significant biological activities in animal model study, such as antipyretic, analgesic, local anaesthetic, anti-ulcer, mast-cell stabilising, hepato-protective, tranquilising and hypotensive activities. In 1991 Thirugnanasambantham *et al.* isolated cerpegin, a pyridine alkaloid, from the fleshy stem of the plant *Ceropegia juncea* together with lupeol²⁷.

Based on spectroscopic methods (IR, UV and NMR) the structure of this alkaloid has been elucidated as 3,4-dioxo-1,1,5-trimethyl-1,3,4,5-tetrahydrofuro[3,4-c]-pyridine (**1**, Fig. 1). The proposed molecular structure of cerpegin based on the spectral data was further confirmed with the help of single crystal X-ray crystallographic studies²⁸. Fused pyridinone and furanone ring planes of cerpegin make an angle of 1.02° and

Fig. 1. Cerpegin.

the crystal structure is stabilized by two intermolecular hydrogen bond of type C-H...O, e.g. C(7)-H(7)...O(2) and C(6)-H(6)...O(amide).

3. Methods of synthesis of cerpegin

Although cerpegin alkaloid is relatively rare in nature, but it has a promising pharmacological profile. Consequently a number of methods have been established for the synthesis of such alkaloid molecule. From strategic point of view these synthetic methods can be categorized into three groups. In the first group lactone moiety is build on a pyridine ring. In the second category pyridine ring of cerpegin is constructed on a γ -lactone. Third group involves concomitant formation of both of the pyridine and lactone ring.

3.1. From pyridine precursors:

Different strategies toward the synthesis of cerpegin from pyridine precursors have been employed.

In 1992 Godard and coworkers reported first synthesis of cerpegin **1** from 2-chloronicotinic acid **4** in six synthetic steps (28% overall yield, Scheme 1)²⁹. The key step for this synthesis is the preparation of hydroxyamide **3** from *ortho*-methoxy-N,N-diisopropylamide **2** based on *ortho*-metalation with TMPLi (lithium 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidide) in THF in the presence of TMEDA.

In independent and parallel work Kelly and Walsh reported an analogous synthesis of cerpegin in the same year (Scheme 2)³⁰. Directed *ortho*-metalation of *ortho*-methoxy-N-*tert*-butylamide **5** with *n*-BuLi in ether, not in THF followed by addition of acetone is found to be crucial step in this synthesis. The overall yield of the synthesis is found to be 21%.

Comins *et al.* carried out the elegant synthesis of cerpegin **1** from commercially available 2-methoxypyridine **6** in 34% overall yield (Scheme 3)³¹. The interesting aspect in this synthesis is to install lactol moiety at the appropriate site of pyridine ring in one step. In this case lactol skeleton in **7** was synthesised in a logical reaction sequence i.e. lithiation (MesLi), addition of N-formyl-N,N',N'-trimethylethylenediamine, directed lithiation (*n*-BuLi), treatment with cerium chloride (CeCl₃) and acetone addition.

In 2004, Sarkar and Basak reported synthesis of cerpegin from azaphthalan **8**³². In connection to the development of a route to geminally alkylated azaphthalans, we documented a consecutive double desilylation-alkylation reaction approach and showed that this novel methodology can be elabo-

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Scheme 1. Synthesis of cerpegin by Godard and coworkers.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of cerpegin by Kelly and Walsh.

rated to cerpegin. Oxidation of geminally methylated azaphthalan **9** with $\text{RuCl}_3\text{-NaIO}_4$ yielded azaphthalide which can be transformed into cerpegin by dechlorination followed by N-methylation.

In 2005 Marsais *et al.* extended their earlier work to the one pot synthesis of cerpegin³³. This one pot strategy utilized lithiation of commercially available 2-methoxynicotinic acid **10**. The lithio intermediate was treated *in situ* with ac-

etone at low temperature followed by acid-catalyzed cyclization of resulting dilithio species and N-alkylation using methyl iodide and cesium carbonate gave the natural product cerpegin **1**.

3.2. From γ -lactone precursors:

There have been several advances in the use of γ -lactone precursor to synthesize cerpegin alkaloid.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of cerpegin by Hong and Comins.

Scheme 4. Synthesis of cerpegin by Sarkar and Basak.

In 1994 Matsuo *et al.* developed a straight forward synthesis of cerpegin **1** in 15% overall yield (Scheme 6)³⁴. Michael addition of phenylthioacetone to 2-methoxycarbonyl-4,4-dimethyl-2-buten-4-olide **11** in presence of LDA gave stereoisomeric mixture of functionalized Michael adduct which on oxidation with mCPBA followed by pyrolytic elimination produced nitrile group bearing α,β -unsaturated-

γ -lactone **12**. Reduction of nitrile group to an amine in the presence of conjugated C-C double bond followed by cyclization are the crucial steps in construction of pyridine on lactone precursor. N-methylation of **13** with methyl *p*-toluenesulphonate in presence of NaH afforded cerpegin alkaloid **1**.

A more practical, efficient and high yield (75%) one pot

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Scheme 5. Synthesis of cerpegin by Marsais and coworkers.

Scheme 6. Synthesis of cerpegin by Matsuo and coworkers.

synthesis of cerpegin **1** was reported by Villemin *et al.* (Scheme 7)³⁵. This one pot synthetic process involved cesium carbonate (Cs_2CO_3) and aliquat phase transfer catalyst mediated condensation of commercially available 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-2-butanone **14** with diethyl malonate yielding ethoxycarbonyl- α,β -unsaturated- γ -lactone **15**, followed by addition of 1,3,5-triazine to the resultant reaction mixture and subsequent addition of MeI for N-methylation of *in situ* generated pyridone. In a subsequent publication they showed that Cs_2CO_3 can be replaced by EtONa/EtOH to make this

one pot synthetic process more economical³⁶.

Matsuo and coworkers completed their second synthesis of cerpegin **1** in 1997³⁷. In their synthesis methyl 3-(2,2-dimethoxyethyl)-4-methyl-4-pentanoate **17** was prepared from (-)-carvone **16** (Scheme 8). Lithium hydroxide mediated hydrolysis followed by iodolactonization (I_2 -KI- NaHCO_3) and subsequent reduction with tri-*n*-butyltin hydride in the presence of azobisisobutyronitrile in benzene gave **18**. Incorporation of carbomethoxy group at the α -position with methyl chloroformate and LDA followed by reductive

Scheme 7. Synthesis of cerpegin by Villemin and Liao.

Scheme 8. Second synthesis of cerpegin by Matsuo and coworkers.

amination with methyl amine and sodium borohydride afforded lactone **19** which on heating with 10% Pd/C in decalin gave cerpegin alkaloid in 81% yield.

In 2010 Avetisyan and Karapetyan showed convenient way of synthesis of cerpegin **1** in 89% overall yield from **20** (Scheme 9)^{38,39}. This route involved condensation of easily

accessible γ -lactone carboxamide **20** with N,N-dimethylformamide dimethylacetal **21** followed by cyclization of *in situ* generated enamine intermediate.

In 2012 Bouvier-Durand group⁴⁰ and Villemin group³⁶ independently pointed out a new and efficient approach for the synthesis of cerpegin. In addition Villemin team extended

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Scheme 9. Synthesis of cerpegin by Avetisyan and Karapetyan.

their earlier findings. In this new approach enamino- γ -lactone ester was synthesized in the first step based on condensation of the 2(5*H*)-furanone **22** with *N,N*-dimethylformamide dimethylacetal **21** under solvent-free conditions (Scheme 10). The second step involved the addition of methylamine to enaminone **23** under solvent-free conditions to

afford cerpegin in excellent yields.

3.3. From pyrimidine precursors:

In 2000 Dehaen and coworkers developed a strategy for the synthesis of fused pyridines from pyrimidine derivatives based on intramolecular hetero-Diels-Alder cycloaddition⁴¹. As an application of this methodology intramolecular cycliza-

Scheme 10. Solvent-free synthesis of cerpegin by Villemin and coworkers.

Scheme 11. Synthesis of cerpegin by Dehaen and coworkers.

tion of suitably methoxy substituted acetylene tethered pyridine **24** at elevated temperature yielded furo-[3,4-c]pyridine derivative **25** from which alkaloid cerpegin **1** can be prepared by N-methylation with MeI in 90% overall yield (Scheme 11).

4. Cerpegin analogues

4.1. N^5 derivatives of cerpegin:

A series of N-derivatives of cerpegin are known in the literature, in which the only chemical modification is in the alkyl group attached to the nitrogen atom of cerpegin alkaloid⁴⁰. Some important analogues of this category, **26-35** are shown in Fig. 2.

Bouvier-Durand and coworkers synthesized a range of N^5 analogues of cerpegin from enamino- γ -lactone ester **23** upon treatment with a variety of amines (b.p. > 100°C) in refluxing xylene (*cf.* Scheme 10). When amine components are of lower boiling points, they made a variation on the strategy and used Avetisyan's method^{38,39} for the synthesis of another range of N-derivatives of cerpegin from a variety of γ -lactone carboxamide **20** (*cf.* Scheme 9). Starting lactones are mostly commercially available and could be synthesized by condensation of the corresponding ketoalcohols with diethyl malonate in the presence of catalytic amount of sodium ethylate (*cf.* Scheme 7).

Several N-alkyl analogues of cerpegin were also synthesized by Villemin group³⁶. To establish the scope of their earlier findings they utilized one pot synthesis involving 1,3,5-triazine and alkyl halides (Scheme 7). These synthetic derivatives of cerpegin can be used for bioassay.

4.2. C^1 derivatives of cerpegin:

Synthetic C^1 analogues of cerpegin can be interesting candidates in the pharmaceutical research. Some important analogues of this category, **36-38** are displayed in Fig. 3⁴². These C^1 derivatives of cerpegin are synthesized based on 1,3,5-triazine mediated one step process (*cf.* Scheme 7) or from the methylamine mediated treatment of enamino- γ -lactone ester in refluxing xylene⁴⁰ (Scheme 10).

4.3. C^1 and N^5 disubstituted derivatives of cerpegin:

A wide variety of novel cerpegin derivatives substituted at N^5 and C^1 positions were designed. Some specific analogues in this category, **39-42** are shown in Fig. 4. The synthesis of these disubstituted analogues began with suitably substituted γ -lactone ester e.g. substituted **22** which was transformed into corresponding enamino- γ -lactone ester **23** (*cf.* Scheme 10)⁴². The key intermediate **23** was then treated with aromatic or aliphatic amines or hydrazines (hydrazine monohydrate and methyl hydrazine) to afford a variety of desired disubstituted cerpegin derivatives.

Further, Villemin's 1,3,5-triazine mediated one pot process can also provide rapid access to disubstituted cerpegin derivatives³⁶.

4.4. C^1 and C^4 disubstituted derivatives of cerpegin:

C^1 and C^4 disubstituted cerpegin derivatives with main variations of the functional groups at C^4 position are reported in literature^{43,44}. Fig. 5 shows some promising analogues of cerpegin with structure, e.g. **43-47**.

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Fig. 2. Synthetic N⁵ analogues of cerpegin.

Fig. 3. Synthetic C¹ analogues of cerpegin.

C⁴-hydroxy, C¹ alkyl disubstituted cerpegin derivatives are conveniently prepared based on the reaction of easily accessible carbonitriles **48** with DMF-DMA (Scheme 12). Dimethylaminovinyl derivatives **49** so formed undergo further cyclization when exposed to AcOH/HCl mixture (3:1) and form desired hydroxyl substituted cerpegin derivatives **50** in

high yields.

In addition, dimethylaminovinyl derivatives **49** can be converted into primary 4-amino cerpegin derivatives **52** in high yields by reacting with 20% ammonia. For the synthesis of disubstituted cerpegin derivatives **55** with substituted amino function at C⁴ position, the 4-chlorocerpegin deriva-

Fig. 4. Synthetic C¹ and N⁵ disubstituted analogues of cerpegin.

Fig. 5. Synthetic C¹ and C⁴ disubstituted analogues of cerpegin.

tives **53**, obtained from the treatment of C⁴-hydroxy substituted cerpegin derivatives with PCl_5 at 130–150°C, is to be treated with corresponding amines.

Similar reactions can also be carried out to synthesize 4-thioxo derivatives **54** from the corresponding thiocarboxamides **51** without isolating intermediate dimethylaminovinyl derivatives and starting thiocarboxamides are obtained from carbonitriles **48**.

The same synthetic procedure has been applied to syn-

thesize 4-methyl cerpegin derivatives from 3-acetyl-furan-2(5*H*)-one compounds i.e. through the corresponding dimethylaminovinyl intermediates followed by ring formation in the presence of ammonia.

4.5. Bis-cerpegin:

Bis-cerpegin derivatives can be promising candidates in the drug development research. A few selected bis-cerpegin derivatives of this category, e.g. **56-58** are shown in Fig. 6. These dimeric derivatives **60** can be prepared by addition of

Scheme 12. Synthesis of cerpegin analogues by Bouvier-Durand group.

an equivalent of different diamines to two equiv. of suitably substituted enaminolactone **59** in DMF under refluxing conditions (Scheme 13)³⁶.

5. Pharmacological studies

The natural pyridine alkaloid cerpegin has been shown to exhibit diverse biological and pharmacological activities. It possesses analgesic, tranquillizer, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer and anti-ulcer properties^{45,46,25}. Further investigations on biological activities of the molecules containing this fused furo-pyridine ring system have shown that these compounds can be used as anti-hypertensive⁴⁷, diuretics⁴⁸, anti-allergic^{49,50} and antibacterial⁵¹. The tubers of many *Ceropegia* species are used by tribal women to promote fertility and also used in the treatment of diarrhea, dysentery and treatment of urinary bladder stones⁵²⁻⁵⁴. Furthermore, furo-pyri-

dines are also useful for inhibiting protein tyrosine kinase⁵⁵ and for preventing and treating cancers⁵⁶.

5.1. Analgesic activity:

Analgesics are agents which selectively relieve pain by acting in the CNS and peripheral pain mediators without changing consciousness. Cerpegin exhibits a dose related analgesic effect (not involving the opioid pathway) against acetic acid induced writhing in mice^{25,45,57}. It does not produce any automatic or behavioral changes up to a dose of 20 mg/kg but doses of more than 400 mg/kg produce excitation and later convulsions and respiratory paralysis in mice.

5.2. Tranquillizer activity:

The alkaloidal fraction of the *Ceropegia* plant extract exhibits promising tranquillizing properties^{46,25}. A tranquillizer is a drug that acts on the CNS and help to slow down brain

Fig. 6. Some bis-cerpegin analogues.

Scheme 13. Synthesis of bis-cerpegin.

activity and relieve overactive nerves. Taking this medication can help people to calm, decrease anxiety or help a person to sleep. It is also used to treat mental illness that are characteristic of the psychoses (e.g. Schizophrenia) which is a behavioral disorder. It can cause dependence and certain ones can easily be abused. The exact mechanism is not known. Plausible mechanisms of action are competitive blockade of dopamine (D_2) receptors and serotonin receptors. It may be mentioned here that triterpenoids present in the *Ceropegia* extract may have some role on the tranquillizing properties.

5.3. Proteasome inhibitors activity:

The proteasome plays crucial role in the regulation and maintenance of a diverse array of basic cellular processes (e.g. cell proliferation) by degrading misfolded proteins^{58,59}. The balance of protein synthesis and degradation is tightly regulated in healthy and normal cells. Inhibition of proteasome should prevent malignant cells from proliferation and therefore proteasome inhibitors have emerged as promising molecules in a number of therapies and particularly as anticancer

drugs⁶⁰. Proteasome inhibitors can block cell division, inflammation through inhibition of NF- κ B activation, generation of antigenic peptides and can induce apoptosis.

The intracellular ATP-dependent proteasome (26S) is composed of a cylindrical catalytic core (20S) and two regulatory complexes (19S) located at both ends of the 20S cylinder (Fig. 7)^{61,62}. The catalytic core comprises four stacked heptameric rings with two inner β rings surrounded by one α ring on each side ($\alpha_{1-7} \beta_{1-7} \beta_{1-7} \alpha_{1-7}$). The different proteolytic activities are confined to the two identical inner β rings. In a single β ring, only the β_1 , β_2 and β_5 subunits possess a proteolytic activity^{63,64}. Caspase-like or PA (post-

acid) proteolytic active sites are found in the β_1 subunit and cleave peptide bonds after acidic residues. β_5 subunit has chymotrypsin-like (CT-L) proteolytic specificity and cut peptide bonds after hydrophobic residues. Trypsin-like (T-L) proteolytic activity is due to β_2 subunit and cleave peptide bonds preferentially after basic residues. Each type of proteolytic site possesses a threonine residue at position 1 capable of nucleophilic attack on the substrates.

Various synthetic inhibitors with different inhibitory profiles towards the proteolytic activities of the 26S proteasome have been identified^{58,59}. In 2003, Bortezomib (PS-341, Velcade), peptide boronate inhibitor, became the first proteasome inhibitor approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of multiple myeloma and is now undergoing clinical trials for many other types of cancer (Fig. 8)⁶⁵. However, despite its high efficiency, a large proportion of patients do not achieve sufficient clinical response. Therefore, the development of a second-generation of proteasome inhibitors (PIs) with improved pharmacological properties was needed. Salinosporamide A (Sal A), natu-

Fig. 7. Structure of 26S proteasome.

ral second generation inhibitor, having fused γ -lactam- β -lactone bicyclic ring structure is a potent inhibitor (IC_{50} 0.43 μ M) of all three proteolytic activities⁶⁶. Likewise, the natural alkaloid cerpegin bearing fused lactam-lactone rings has been shown to inhibit the PA proteolytic activity of proteasome in the micromolar range (IC_{50} 10.4 μ M). But Sal A did not inhibit selectively PA activity as cerpegin do.

To optimize proteasome inhibition Bouvier-Durand and coworkers synthesized a considerable number of new N^5 cerpegin analogues and bioassay of these derivatives was carried out⁴⁰. N^5 -Cerpegin derivative **26** is reported to inhibit PA activity (IC_{50} 4.9 μ M) with no or only low effect on the CT-L or T-L active sites. Inhibitor **29** bearing N-pyrrolidiny propyl (IC_{50} 11.4 μ M) is twice less efficient inhibitor of the PA activity than compound **26**. The 2-chloro phenethyl and the 4-sulfonamide phenethyl compounds, **32** (IC_{50} 4.9 μ M) and **33** (IC_{50} 5.5 μ M), respectively, are around 4-fold more efficient than the 4-chloro phenethyl compound **30** (IC_{50} 20.1

μ M) and almost 10-fold more efficient than the 4-fluoro phenethyl compound (**31**). In addition PA inhibitory effects of **27** (IC_{50} 6.1 μ M) and **28** (IC_{50} 5.2 μ M) are found to be slightly less than analogue **26**.

In subsequent publication Bouvier-Durand group demonstrated the possibility to design C^1 and N^5 disubstituted derivatives of cerpegin for further optimization of PA inhibitory activities⁴². Accordingly synthesis and bioassay of a variety of C^1 and N^5 derivatives of cerpegin were carried out. Almost all molecules are inefficient in inhibiting the activity of both calpain I and cathepsin B. A set of sixteen disubstituted cerpegin derivatives are found to be active specifically against Post Acid (PA) activity of 20S proteasome in the micromolar range. Two of them, namely **39** and **40**, have IC_{50} values close to 2 μ M. Interestingly, inhibitors **39** and **40** have a phenethyl group at C^1 and this substitution produces higher potency to inhibitors relative to the parent 1,1-dimethylated analogs, depending on the stereochemistry.

Based on earlier results on efficient N^5 substituents, same research group synthesized C^4 - and C^1 -substituted cerpegin derivatives with main variations of the functional groups at C^4 position⁴³. Compound **45** with a C^4 -substituted benzylamino group strongly inhibited the PA activity of c20S proteasome (IC_{50} of 600 nM). At the whole cell level, compound **45** also inhibited PA activity of HeLa cervical cancer cell line (IC_{50} cel = 11.6 \pm 0.6 μ M). At these concentrations no cytotoxicity was found. Only higher concentrations were found to be mildly cytotoxic.

To highlight the binding mechanism of cerpegin derivatives "In silico molecular docking" experiment was performed by Bouvier-Durand *et al.*^{40,42,43} and showed that bicyclic ring

Fig. 8. First and second generation proteasome inhibitors.

system of the cerpegin derivative fits into a groove in the active site (β_1 subunit) between Thr21 and Thr1. The N⁵ nitrogen atom lies at about the same distance from the amide oxygens of Thr21 and Gly47. Both the furan ring oxygen atom and lactone oxygen atom lie close to the amine hydrogen of Thr1, whereas lactam oxygen atom lies close to the amine hydrogen of Thr21. The N⁵ substituent most often makes favourable contacts with the aromatic ring of Tyr114 of the β_2 subunit and this possible involvement is absent from the catalytic site of the two other proteolytic activities. When the N⁵ substituent comprised one or several polar group(s), the poses predict the possibility of hydrogen bond formation with the carbonyl oxygen of Thr21 in β_1 and/or the side chain alcohol of Ser118 in β_2 . C¹ substituents are located in a rather hydrophobic groove running into Tyr30 in subunit β_7 and lined by the peptide groups of Gly129 and Ser130 on one side and by the side chains of Met residues 95 and 116 of β_1 on the other side. This hydrophobic groove of the β_1 subunit is responsible for the primed substrate binding or specificity channel of the PA activity. However, Thr10^γ is shown to react with electrophilic lactone group of inhibitor cerpegin derivatives.

5.4. Antiurolithiatic activity:

Urolithiasis is most common disease of the urinary tract. It is a process of development of crystals either in the kidney or in any part of urinary tract, including ureters and bladder⁶⁷. Urinary stone formation takes place due to a change in urinary chemistry such as hypercalciuria and hyperoxaluria, leading to urinary supersaturation which later crystallizes, aggregates and ends up in stone formation. The primary constituent of urolithiasis is either calcium oxalate/calcium oxalate mixed with calcium phosphate (75–90%) or magnesium ammonium phosphate (5–10%). The type of stone formed in human can be predicted from the pH of the fasting urine. If the pH is acidic 5.0 or below, the stones likely to form are of uric acid type, if 5.0–6.5 calcium oxalate type and if alkaline, i.e. pH above 7.0 magnesium ammonium phosphate type. Antiurolithiatic activity indicates inhibition of stone formation or dissolution of preformed stones as well. Decoction of Tubers of *Ceropegia bulbos* (L.) is used to remove urinary bladder stone^{67,68}. In 2012 M. Jain reported that cerpegin alkaloid is able to dissolve both calcium oxalate and preferably calcium phosphate, thereby exhibiting

antiurolithiatic activity⁶⁹. Therefore on administration of cerpegin alkaloid, deposition of urinary calculi should be significantly reduced.

5.5. Miscelenious activity of *ceropegia* extracts:

The hydro-alcoholic extract of *Ceropegia juncea* whole plant is reported to exhibit hepatoprotective activity against paracetamol induced hepatic damage and significant antioxidant activity in rats⁷⁰. The stem extracts of this plant showed antioxidant as well as antibacterial activity against some bacteria^{71,72}.

Neutrophil elastase is a serine protease that hydrolyzes the proteins within the azurophilic granules of the neutrophils. Once secreted, it digests collagen-VI and elastin of the extracellular matrix and is responsible for HNE associated diseases. The dichloromethane extract from *Ceropegia rupicola* plant has been found to inhibit the activity of human neutrophil elastase, a serine proteases⁷³.

The dichloromethane extract of *Ceropegia fusca* showed significant cytostatic activity against HL-60, A-431 and SK-MEL-1 cells, human leukemic, epidermoid carcinoma and melanoma cells, respectively. Darias *et al.*⁷⁴ reported the cicatrizing, haemostatic and chemotherapeutic properties that are traditionally attributed in this species.

In 2017 Kalimuthu *et al.* pointed out antidiabetic and anti-inflammatory activity of ethanol and methanol extracts of *in vivo* and *in vitro* plants of *Ceropegia juncea*⁷⁵. Antidiabetic activity was studied using α -amylase inhibitory assay and α -glycosidase inhibitory assay, whereas anti-inflammatory activity was evaluated using albumin denaturation assay and membrane stabilization assay.

6. Summary and outlook

It is clear from foregoing discussion that cerpegin is a rare and key compound of the genus *Ceropegia*. In view of potential pharmacological profile a number of synthetic strategies for synthesis of cerpegin alkaloid have been developed. I have attempted to present a comprehensive view of the various synthetic avenues to bioactive cerpegin as well as cerpegin derivatives. Cerpegin alkaloid has been the subject of previous review with special emphasis on *in vitro* propagation of threatened *Ceropegia* plant and *in vitro* propagation techniques might prove helpful in the cultivation of plant and production of the cerpegin alkaloid as well. But, to date,

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a comprehensive review on its chemical synthesis and pharmacological profile has not been available. Herein, I additionally overviewed the biological activities of this alkaloid.

There is, however, still scope for improvements such as even milder, general approaches towards its synthesis. Exploration of new pharmacological profile for cerpegin alkaloid has gained considerable interest in recent years. Although *Ceropegia* extract, in some cases, is reported to be biologically active, but exact role of cerpegin alkaloid need to be explored. Furthermore, to improve diverse biological and pharmacological activities of cerpegin alkaloid more and more cerpegin analogues are need to prepare for structure-activity relationship (SAR) studies. Overall, I hope that this review is expected to stimulate further developments and renew academic interest in the chemistry of cerpegin alkaloid.

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